

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D3.4.1

A comprehensive overview of all ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are active will be established and available (Knowledge Hub and OneStop)

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2022-12 | Version: 1.0

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8138481](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8138481)

nfdi4earth.de

Citation

Valentina Protopopova-Kakar, Florian Ott, Wolfgang zu Castell-Rüdenhausen, Frederik Tilmann. 2023. *A comprehensive overview of all ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are active will be established and available (Knowledge Hub and OneStop) (NFDI4Earth Deliverable D3.4.1)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8138481>

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Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through the project NFDI4Earth (DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>) within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, <https://www.nfdi.de/>).

Executive summary

This report summarizes the initial version of the overview of all Earth System Science (ESS) relevant Research Data Management (RDM) networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are active.

The first part of this comprehensive overview presents the additional value that the collected information could bring to the NFDI4Earth community - an improved level of information about the available international opportunities in various RDM and/or ESS initiatives, offering a direct contact through their German representatives. The collected data will be stored in the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub (KH), periodically updated and will be easily accessible through the NFDI4Earth One Stop for All (OS4A).

Four main different types of initiatives are distinguished (Communities and Accusations; Data Infrastructures; Data, Software, Services and Educational & Training materials providers; Projects), which are listed in the second section of the document. The future networking approach to each of the groups is built on the existing commitment of participants in NFDI4Earth and their active engagement to each initiative.

The data collection approach, based primary on internet survey, is presented in the third part of the report. The document outlines a future step to gather information through direct contact with NFDI4Earth participants to obtain all necessary information and keep it up-to-date.

Glossary and terminology

D3.4.1 Deliverable 3.4.1 - "A comprehensive overview of all ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are active will be established and available (Knowledge Hub and OneStop)"

D3.4.2 Deliverable 3.4.2 - "Key stake holders and contact persons are included"

DKRZ - German Climate Computing Center (Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum), see <https://www.dkrz.de/en>

DFG - German Research Foundation, see <https://www.dfg.de/en/>

GFZ - Helmholtz Centre Potsdam GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, see <https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/en/>

EduTrain - Education and Training Materials and Services

EOSC - European Open Science Cloud, see <https://www.eosc-portal.eu>

ESS - Earth System Sciences

FAIR - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability [2]

KH - Knowledge Hub

LHB - Living Hand Book

M2.3 - Measure 2.3. Governmental Data

M2.4 - Measure 2.4. Data in Long-Term Storage

M3.3 - Measure 3.3. NFDI Commons

M3.4 - Measure 3.4. International Networking & Embedding

M4.2 - Measure 4.2. Towards a Cultural Change in ESS Research Data Management

NFDI - National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur), see <http://www.nfdi.de>

NFDI4Earth - NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences / NFDI Konsortium Erdsystemforschung, see <https://www.nfdi4earth.de>

OS - Open Science

OS4A - One Stop for All

RDM - Research Data Management

TA2 - Task Area 2, 2 Facilitate, NFDI4Earth

TA3 - Task Area 3, 2 Interoperate, NFDI4Earth

TUD - Technische Universität Dresden, see <https://tu-dresden.de/>

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1. Introduction

The NFDI4Earth brings together the broad range of the German ESS community in a new, innovative way. Many existing national and international communities are making efforts on their own to improve the FAIRness of published data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) in their discipline, and we would like to involve them in the NFDI4Earth initiative to unite efforts for a cultural change across research disciplines and borders [1].

The overall goal of Measure 3.4. (M3.4) is to ensure and promote international awareness of NFDI4Earth and support the development of advanced RDM culture by connecting and actively participating in international initiatives. The long-term operation of NFDI4Earth, which is fully embedded in a well-functioning National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI - Nationale ForschungsDatenInfrastruktur) operation model, is the primary target. Embedding of this kind will specifically address the way researchers are guided by international policies and standards in RDM. Harmonizing standards and agreement on common core standards is needed (e.g. in the context of metadata, vocabularies, encodings, application programming and service interfaces) are needed as a foundation for interoperability [1].

The long-term perspective for NFDI4Earth is to be linked and embedded into European and international initiatives and research data infrastructures [1].

2. Purpose

The purpose of this first deliverable from M3.4, entitled **"A comprehensive overview of all ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are active will be established and available (Knowledge Hub and OneStop)"** is to collect existing and active RDM-related initiatives among the NFDI4Earth community. The collected information will be supplemented by deliverable D3.4.2, entitled "Key stake holders and contact persons are included", by the end of quarter 3 (Q3) of 2023. The final goal of both deliverables is to collect information that is to be stored in the NFDI4Earth KH and is easily accessible by NFDI4Earth users through the NFDI4Earth OS4A. This will lead to an improved level of information for users and ESS service providers in Germany about the available international opportunities in various RDM initiatives, offering the direct contact through the German representatives.

Currently, the information is stored in an Excel spreadsheet in the Technische Universität Dresden (TUD) SharePoint until the KH becomes available. At this point, the overall table contains more than 220 initiatives (national, international and national with international significance) that are active at least until December 2022. The metadata (table headers) are in accordance with the KH (Measure 3.2).

3. Collaborations

Measure 3.3 (M3.3 - national) and M3.4 (international) networking activities have been initially synchronized their actions in the collection of information and both teams are in close communication with each other. The overview tables with national and international RDM initiatives were re-structured and merged. Currently, the collection of international RDM activities is complete (summarized in this document).

M3.3, M3.4 and M4.2 (Measure 4.2 - Towards a Cultural Change in ESS Research Data Management) agreed that each Measure should prepare by the end of January 2023 up to two-pages concept with the ideas about the main target groups and multipliers respectively, the relevant key messages and offers respective on a short-, mid- and long-term perspective. The three measures agreed to work together in the networking activities to ensure synchronized efforts. The responsible people from Measure 2.3, Governmental Data, will be included in the synchronized networking activities.

4. Mid-term vision

The missing key stake holders and the contact information will be gathered until Q3 2023 by all NFDI4Earth Co-applicants and Participants, as part of D4.3.2, and the table will be completed. Once the KH is ready for use, the information will be transferred, if necessary the table will be restructured, or the (meta)data will be included or excluded according to the KH configuration. The information will be long-term stored in the KH and will be updated periodically (at least once a year). The final goal is for the people, who are involved in each initiative, to become engaged with the NFDI4Earth concept and personally take care of keeping the KH information up-to-date (especially contact information).

M3.3 is also responsible for the development and management of the Living HandBook (LHB) – an editable comprehensive ESS “encyclopaedia”, containing easy to understand, accessible and transparent documentation of the NFDI4Earth products, architecture, structure, services and innovations. Chapters of this LHB will be internationally recognized “FAIR standards [2] and regulations for data and machine-readable metadata”, “Open Science (OS) standards”, “Research Data Commons”, “Best (and failed) practices information”, etc., which is planned to be provided by the involved people from different initiatives. Here M3.3 and M3.4 will work together.

5. Initiatives Scope

5.1. Communities/Associations

The international community discussions to establish FAIR and OS standards, regulations, policies, vocabularies, encodings, application programming and service interfaces for community data and machine-readable metadata, guidelines (set of standards and technical explanation how to use these standards) are the first step towards a cultural change for data interoperability. The overall goals and the mission of each Community are sometimes unclear, and the Communities' efforts in cultural change are rarely publicly known. We would like to give better publicity to all International and German Communities' activities, store the available documentation for data interoperability in the LHB, that will be easily findable by all ESS researchers and accessible through the OS4A.

Building on the existing commitment of participants in NFDI4Earth, M3.4 will provide and use capacities and services for acquiring, sharing and processing ESS data and ensure the development of new opportunities of RDM by connecting and actively participating in international initiatives [1].

As a next step, the NFDI4Earth will take part in the existing collaborations, connections, memberships in all ESS-relevant networks and initiatives to connect and report/disseminate NFDI4Earth ideas and activities [1].

5.1.1. International ESS Communities and Associations

NFDI4Earth participants and co-applicants are active members of international ESS communities and associations (e.g. AGU, EGU, IUGG, IPCC, Geo.8 and many more). These communities are all dealing with RDM on a broad scale, from policies to services. The establishment of FAIR data and software standards, based on the community needs and requirements (in any scientific field) is a key component of establishment of cross-discipline interoperable data.

5.1.2. International ESS Communities and Associations with RDM focus

NFDI4Earth is, due to its members, actively involved in many international initiatives such as COPERNICUS, ENES, ENVRI-FAIR, EPOS, FluxNet, eLTER, ORFEUS/EIDA, ICOS. In this way, NFDI4Earth covers all relevant aspects of ESS internationally and can also benefit from these networks and engagements in terms of the ongoing establishment of accepted standards and the implementation of international directives (such as INSPIRE) [1]. Participation in international standardization bodies will allow NFDI4Earth to benefit from the international developments and protect the common needs of NFDI in terms of RDM development.

5.1.3. International RDM Communities and Associations beyond ESS scope

NFDI4Earth participants are active members of international RDM communities and associations beyond the ESS scope, such as RDA, Codata, WDS, FORCE11, W3C, OGC, OpenAIRE, as well as have strong integration into and with general data-related services such as DataCite, ePIC, re3data, ORCID, ROR, GeoROC, or MetBase. These initiatives provide general RDM services and support the cross-disciplinary interoperability.

5.2. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), EOSC's Projects and other countries' national data infrastructures

NFDI4Earth is, through its members, actively engaged in many EOSC's Projects like Geo-INQUIRE, FAIR is FAIR, ENVRI Future, EOSC-Pillar, FAIRCORE4EOSC, etc. NFDI is the German contributor and provider of RDM services for EOSC. In order to fulfil the EOSC's requirements for international quality services, the NFDI Consortia has to provide a RDM development first on national level. NFDI4Earth would like to synchronize the efforts with other countries' national data infrastructures and avoid "reinventing the wheel".

5.3. Providers of Data/Software/Training materials

NFDI4Earth members are also actively participating in different initiatives, that provide data, software or training materials in ESS (ORFEUS, INTERMAGNET, INSPIRE, EPOS, UNU, etc.). An easy access to many of these international services is important for NFDI4Earth users in order to provide interdisciplinary research, based on international standards. Also, in case of a lack of certain ESS services in the German marketplace, NFDI4Earth would like to provide easy access via OS4A to some internationally represented services to fill the gap. The networking activities of M3.4 can facilitate this connection.

5.4. Projects (not EOSC related)

NFDI4Earth members participate in many ESS projects (CMIP, CORE-Climax, eLTER, GlolbeDraught, FAIR WISH etc.). The future of some of these projects is unclear, and it is most likely the produced data or software to be lost or stored locally after the projects end, with a risk of data not being published FAIRly and preserved in the long term. NFDI4Earth would like to offer a possibility for the data (and software) to be long-term preserved (responsibility of M2.4 - Data in Long-Term Storage) and made available to the extensive NFDI4Earth community.

6. Data collection

6.1. Approach

- Based on the information written in the letters of intent (provided by each potential NFDI4Earth Participant in early 2019 prior to the first proposal draft) for various initiatives, we were able to start the overview of the ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are active (see Fig. 1). The rest of the necessary information about the available initiatives was collected from their web pages and corrected wherever this information diverges from that in the letters of intent (e.g. involved and/or responsible organizations, projects due dates, etc.).
- The table was complemented with all initiatives mentioned in the NFDI4Earth's Project Proposal [1] and the lacking information was collected from their web pages.
- A manual search in the NFDI4Earth Participants' web pages was done as a next step, but unfortunately some of NFDI4Earth partners don't keep up-to-date or/and public information about engagement of their employees in different projects, associations, standardization bodies etc. Good examples for well-provided information about different initiatives and people involved within the organization are the web sites of the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) or the Helmholtz Centre Potsdam German Research Centre for Geosciences (GFZ). Both Organizations' web pages offer easy search options and provide relevant results, but still not all information is up-to-date.
- Interlinking between different web pages provided many potentially interesting initiatives in ESS or/and RDM, that were further added in the table, but for some of them the German commitment information is not publicly available.
- The table was complemented with information provided by many of the NFDI4Earth Co-apps and Participants (especially from Task Areas 2 and 3, as TA's with higher number of Participants) in personal conversations, online meetings and email correspondence with the initiatives that they are personally involved (National and international).
- An additional review of about 60 EOSC Projects was carried out, all ESS related projects were reviewed, and only ongoing projects of potential interest to NFDI4Earth were retained.
- For the purpose of the future networking activities, the information was supplemented with potentially interesting national data infrastructures of other countries, although it is clear that none of the NFDI4Earth Participants are involved.
- The table was reviewed by TUD members, two of the existing initiatives were removed as not up-to-date, but others three were added.

Presented with XMind

Figure 1: ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are active, based on the letters of engagement

- The table was reviewed by members of M3.3 and additional information was added on national and some national initiatives of international importance. Duplicate information was deleted.

6.2. Current view of the table

The overall table contains about 220 national, international and national initiatives of international importance, with 146 internationally related initiatives (Appendix 2 – providing only a general information). The table metadata was initially unified with the repositories table (metadata unified with Re3data, responsibility of M3.1), but later the table with the networking initiatives increased the number of the columns listed below, as a result of the different needs of the networking. The information about all German data repositories (many of them with international importance) was deleted from the networking table and kept only in the repositories table in order to avoid duplication of information and effort.

A review of all collected projects has been done and the projects/initiatives, which are ended were also removed from the table.

In the current table, the collected important information about the initiatives is:

- Title / Abbreviation;
- Full name (if it has)
- ROR identifier (if it has)
- Scope (Infrastructure / repository, Archive, Project, Registry, Union / Society, University / Research institution, Software / Tool);
- Area of Activity (international, national, federal, regional);
- Partners / Members in Germany;
- Partners / Members from NFDI4Earth
- ROR identifier (NFDI4Earth Partners/Members);
- Contact information / respondents (e-mails / telephone numbers and ORCID identifier NFDI4Earth Partners/Members)
- Contact Institution (general);
- Contact information (respondents, e-mails/telephone numbers and ORCID identifier) for many of the initiatives is also collected
- Working duration (permanent, running, ended, created);
- Projects duration (Start-End date);

- URL;
- Product category – potentially interesting services for NFDI4Earth (Data, Software, Knowledge, Consulting, Service, Education, etc.);
- Access (paywall / commercial, on request, open, registration);
- DFG subject areas;
- Description;
- Notes/ Comments.

We have also collected additional information for some of the initiatives, that we consider useful but not important:

- Hosting Institution;
- Partners/Members (International);
- Type of institution (Helmholtz, Leibnitz, NFDI, etc. for the national);
- State (in Germany);
- Is the website maintained;
- Own data policy or OGC standards (for repositories);
- Data access? (own repository, link to other repositories, PIDs);
- Data interoperability (metadata standards);
- Metadata/Data curation.

6.3. Next steps

A request to provide contact information for all RDM initiatives will be sent to all Co-applicants and Participants after completing the table, including all national initiatives. With this action we also aim to preserve only the active initiatives and fill the gaps in ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are involved. The work will continue until Q3 of 2023 with fulfilling the D3.4.2 "Key stake holders and contact persons are included".

7. Conclusion

In this initial version of the overview of all ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives in which NFDI4Earth participants are active, we have collected information about 146 publicly available initiatives (see Appendix 2). In this comprehensive overview, we have distinguished several types of initiatives and marked the future networking approach to each of them. The long-term perspective is that the collected information will be stored in the KH, will be easily accessed by the NFDI4Earth users through OS4A, and all documents related to a certain initiative will be presented in LHB. This will lead to an improved level of information for users and ESS service providers in Germany and beyond about the available international opportunities in different RDM initiatives.

This report will be updated with more detailed specifications after the fulfillment of D3.4.2, as well as annually based on the development of the networking activities and the state of the all NFDI4Earth infrastructure components at the end of each year.

February, 2023, Valentina Protopopova-Kakar, NFDI4Earth Project M3.4 coordination

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Christin Henzen, Thomas Rose and Ira Gerloff for their support, advices and contributions to the table.

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- [1] L. Bernard et al. 2021. "NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences - Proposal 2020 revised," 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5718944>
- [2] M.D. Wilkinson, et al, 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific data, vol. 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

A. A comprehensive overview of all ESS relevant RDM networks and initiatives

N	Title	Full name	Scope	URL
1	IS-ENES	InfraStructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling	Infrastructure / Repository	https://is.enes.org/
2	COPERNICUS	COPERNICUS Data Center	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.copernicus.eu/en
3	CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project	Project	https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/ https://www.cesm.ucar.edu/projects/CMIP6/ http://www.cesm.ucar.edu/projects/CMIP6 https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip
4	ESMValTool	Earth System Model Evaluation Tool	Software / Tool	https://www.esmvaltool.org/
5	EPOS	European Plate Observing System	Project / Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.epos-eu.org/
6	IGSN	The International GeoSample Number	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.igsn.org/resources/ https://www.geosamples.org/ https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/igsn/
7	HYSOMA	Hyperspectral SOil Mapper	Software / Tool	http://www-app2.gfz-potsdam.de/hysoma/?file=main
8	ORFEUS	Observatories & Research Facilities for European Seismology	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.orfeus-eu.org
9	FDSN	International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks	Union / Society	http://www.fdsn.org/
10	IUGG	International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics	Union / Society	http://www.iugg.org/
11	IACS	International Association of Cryospheric Sciences	Union / Society	http://www.cryosphericciences.org
12	IAG	International Association for Geodesy (IAG)	Union / Society	https://www.iag-aig.org/
13	IAGA	International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy	Union / Society	http://www.iaga-aiga.org/
14	IAHS	International Association of Hydrological Sciences	Union / Society	http://iahs.info
15	IAMAS	International Association of Meteorology and Atmospheric Sciences	Union / Society	http://www.iamas.org
16	IAPSO	International Association for the Physical Sciences of the Oceans	Union / Society	https://iapso-ocean.org/
17	IASPEI	International Association of Seismology and Physics of the Earth's Interior	Union / Society	http://www.iaspei.org
18	IAVCEI	International Association of Volcanology and Chemistry of the Earth's Interior	Union / Society	http://www.iavceivolcano.org
19	IAHS	International Association of Hydrogeologists the World-wide Groundwater Organisation	Union / Society	https://iah.org/
20	IAH - Deutschland	The International Association of Hydrogeologists	Union / Society	https://germany.iah.org/
21	EurAqua	the European Network of Freshwater Research Organisations	Union / Society	https://www.euraqua.org/
22	EEA	The European Environment Agency	Union / Society	https://www.eea.europa.eu/
23	ISDRS	International Society for Sustainable Development Research	Union / Society	https://isdrs.org/
24	IWRA	International Water Resources Association	Union / Society	https://www.iwra.org/
25	ISPRS	The International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing	Union / Society	https://www.isprs.org/
26	EARSeL	European Association of Remote Sensing Laboratories	Union / Society	https://earsel.org/
27	EGU	European Geosciences Union	Union / Society	https://www.egu.eu
28	AGU	American Geophysical Union	Union / Society	https://www.agu.org/
29	INTERMAGNET	International Real-time Magnetic Observatory Network	Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool	https://intermagnet.github.iohttps://
30	SeaDataNET	Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management	Project / Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool	https://www.seadatanet.org/About-us/SeaDataCloud
31	CORE-CLIMAX	CORE-CLIMAX	Project	https://www.coreclimax.eu/

N	Title	Full name	Scope	URL
32	eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research (International Long-Term Ecological Research)	Project	https://elter-ri.eu/
33	LTER-D	International Long-Term Ecological Research - Deutschland	Project	https://www.ufz.de/lter-d/index.php?en=42518
34	UN-SPIDER	United Nations Platform for Space-based Information for Disaster Management and Emergency Response	Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool / Training materials	https://www.un-spider.org/
35	IAMC	the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium	Union / Society	https://www.iamconsortium.org/
36	CAMS	The Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service	Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool	https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/
37	ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.icos-cp.eu/ https://www.icos-infrastruktur.de/en/icos-d/
38	GlobeDrought	Global information system on droughts and their impact	Project	https://grow-globedrought.net/
39	ESERO	The European Space Education Resource Office	Project	https://www.esa.int/Education/Teachers_Corner/European_Space_Education_Resource_Office https://esero.de/
40	IPBES	The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services	Union / Society	https://ipbes.net/
41	IPCC	The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change	Union / Society	https://www.ipcc.ch/join-the-ipcc/
42	DINA	Diversity of Insects in Nature protected Areas	Project / Union / Society	https://www.dina-project.net/wiki/Welcome_to_DINA
43	INSPIRE	Infrastructure for spatial information in Europe	Infrastructure / Repository	https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/
44	WDCC	World Data Centre for Climate	Infrastructure / Repository/ archive	https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/
45	UNU	The United Nations University	University/Research institution	https://unu.edu/ https://flores.unu.edu/en/ https://ehs.unu.edu/
46	DataCite	International Data Citation Initiative e.V.	Registry	https://datacite.org/value.html https://search.datacite.org/repositories/tib.gfz
47	RDA	Research Data Alliance	Union / Society	https://www.rd-alliance.org/
48	RDA-DE	Research Data Alliance - Deutschland	Union / Society	https://www.rda-deutschland.de/
49	WDS	World Data System	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.worlddatasystem.org/
50	ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID	Registry	https://orcid.org/ https://www.orcid-de.org/
51	re3data	Registry of Research Data Repositories	Registry	https://www.re3data.org/
52	W3C	TheWorld Wide Web Consortium	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.w3.org/
53	EUDAT	Collaborative Data Infrastructure Agreement	Project / Software / Tool	https://eudat.eu/
54	B2ACCESS	Identity & authorisation	Software / Tool	https://www.eudat.eu/ https://sp.eudat.eu/catalog/
55	B2SHARE	Store and publish research data	Software / Tool	https://www.eudat.eu/ https://sp.eudat.eu/catalog/
56	B2DROP	Sync and share research data	Software / Tool	https://www.eudat.eu/ https://sp.eudat.eu/catalog/
57	B2FIND	Find research data, research data portal	Software / Tool	https://www.eudat.eu/ https://sp.eudat.eu/catalog/
58	B2SAFE	Keep research data safe via data management policies	Software / Tool	https://www.eudat.eu/ https://sp.eudat.eu/catalog/
59	B2NOTE	Data annotation service to create annotations on research data	Software / Tool	https://www.eudat.eu/ https://sp.eudat.eu/catalog/
60	B2HANDLE	Register your research data with a persistent identifier	Software / Tool	https://www.eudat.eu/ https://sp.eudat.eu/catalog/
61	ENVRI FAIR	Environmental research infrastructure building FAIR services for research, innovation and society	Project	https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/
62	ENVRIplus	Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures	Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool	https://www.envriplus.eu/
63	ECRA	the European Climate Researchers Alliance	Union / Society	http://ecra-climate.eu/index.php
64	Open AIRE	An open Scholarly Communication Infrastructure	Union / Society	https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-and-eosc
65	EOSC-Hub	European Open Science Cloud-Hub	Project / Infrastructure / Repository	https://eosc-hub.eu
66	EOSC-Pillar	coordination and harmonization of national initiatives relevant to EOSC	Project	https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/
67	FAIR is FAIR	Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe	Project	https://www.fairsfair.eu/

N	Title	Full name	Scope	URL
68	ENVRI FUTURE	European Open Science Cloud - FUTURE	Project	https://eoscfuture.eu/
69	FAIRCORE4EOSC	EOSC-Core components to enable a FAIR EOSC ecosystem	Project	https://faircore4eosc.eu/
70	Geo-INQUIRE	Geosphere INfrastructures for QUestions into Integrated REsearch	Project	https://www.geo-inquire.eu/
71	Skills4EOSC	Skills for European Open Science Commons	Project	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/
72	EOSC Focus	European Open Science Cloud - Focus	Project	https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project
73	FAIR-IMPACT	FAIR-IMPACT: Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC	Project	https://www.fair-impact.eu
74	GEOSS	the Global Earth Observation System of Systems	Union / Society / Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.earthobservations.org/geoss.php Portal: https://www.geoportal.org/?m:activeLayerTileId=osm&f:dataSource=dab
75	NDACC	Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change	Union / Society / Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.ndaccdemo.org/ https://ndacc.larc.nasa.gov/
76	ESA	the European Space Agency Data Cubes	Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool	https://www.esa.int/
77	EIDA	Seismic European Integrated Data Archive	Union / Society / Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.orfeus-eu.org/data/eida/
78	EarthCube	EarthCube - transforming the conduct of geosciences research	Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool	https://www.earthcube.org/
79	COPDESS	The Coalition for Publishing Data in the Earth and Space Sciences	Union / Society	https://copdess.org/
80	CTS	CoreTrustSeal	Infrastructure / Repository / Registry	https://www.coretrustseal.org/
81	OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium	Union / Society	https://www.ogc.org/
82	CODATA	Cometee on Data	Union / Society	https://codata.org/
83	FORCE11	The Future of Research Communications and e-Scholarship	Union / Society	https://force11.org/
84	Geo.8	European Alliance for Earth Sciences	Union / Society	https://geo8.eu/
85	ICDP	The International Continental Scientific Drilling Program	Union / Society	https://www.icdp-online.org/
86	ICDP-Germany	The International Continental Scientific Drilling Program-Germany	Union / Society	https://www.icdp.ifg.uni-kiel.de/index.jsp?sessionId=7A08FB2CF8C4F67EDC1390D29D70457D
87	ISO	International Organization for Standardization	Union / Society	https://www.iso.org
88	ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation	Union / Society	https://esgf.llnl.gov/
89	GeoROC	The geochemical GeoROC repository	Regisry	https://georoc.eu/georoc/new-start.asp
90	MetBase	Meteorite Information Database	Regisry	https://metbase.org/
91	CLICCS	Cluster of ExcellenceClimate, Climatic Change, and Society	Union / Society	https://www.cliccs.uni-hamburg.de/
92	EARTH DATA	EARTH DATA PORTAL	Infrastructure / Repository / Software/ Tool	https://earth-data.de/?site=home
93	FAIR WISH	FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association	Project	
94	ICDI	Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure	Infrastructure / Repository / Software/ Tool	https://www.icdi.it/en/
95	PAMbase	The Linux Pluggable Authentication Modules (PAM)	Software/ Tool	https://github.com/gentoo/pambase https://gitweb.gentoo.org/proj/pambase.git/commit/
96	FluxNet	Flux Network (European Flux Database)	Union / Society / Infrastructure / Repository	https://fluxnet.org/
97	Water Science Alliance	Water Science Alliance	Union / Society	https://www.watersciencealliance.org/
98	ePIC	electronic Publication Information Center	Regisry	https://epic.awi.de/
99	EMETSOC	European Meteorological Society	Union / Society	https://www.emetsoc.org/
100	DMG	Deutsche Meteorologische Gesellschaft	Union / Society	https://www.dmg-ev.de/

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101	DAM	Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung / German Marine Research Alliance	Union / Society	https://www.allianz-meeresforschung.de
102	MESOCOSM	An open virtual network for aquatic mesocosm facilities worldwide	Union / Society	https://mesocosm.org/
103	Aquacosm-plus	Network of Leading Ecosystem Scale Experimental AQUatic MesoCOSM Facilities Connecting Rivers, Lakes, Estuaries and Oceans in Europe and beyond	Project / Union / Society	https://www.aquacosm.eu/
104	ESIP	Earth Science Information Partners	Union / Society	https://www.esipfed.org
105	AGILE	Association of Geographic Information Laboratories in Europe	Union / Society	https://agile-online.org
106	ATMO-ACCESS	Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities	Project	https://www.atmo-access.eu/
107	SIOS	The Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System	Union / Society	https://www.sios-svalbard.org/
108	WorldFair	Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice	Project	https://worldfair-project.eu/
109	EUMETSAT	European operational satellite agency for monitoring weather, climate and the environment from space	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.eumetsat.int/
110	ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.ecmwf.int/
111	DestinE	Destination Earth	Project	https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/destination-earth
112	DT-GEO	Digital Twin for GEophysical extremes	Project	https://dtgeo.eu/
113	WMO	the World Meteorological Organization	Union / Society	https://public.wmo.int/en
114	D4Science	Destination Earth	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.d4science.org/about-us
115	Future Earth	A global network of scientists, researchers, and innovators collaborating for a more sustainable planet	Union / Society	https://futureearth.org/
116	EuroMarine	European Marine Research Network	Union / Society	https://euromarinenetwork.eu/
117	Data Terra	The Data Terra research infrastructure	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.data-terra.org
118	DISCO	Distributed System of Scientific Collections	Infrastructure / Repository	https://www.dissco.eu
119	Earth System Data Lab	Earth System Data Lab An online environment for Earth System scientists	Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool	https://eo4society.esa.int/resources/earth-system-data-lab/
120	EGI	EGI: Advanced computing for research	Union / Society	https://www.egi.eu
121	CEOS	Committee on Earth Observatoin Satellites	Union / Society	https://ceos.org/
122	Enlight	European university Network to promote equitable quality of Life, sustainability and Global engagement through Higher education Transformation	Union / Society	https://enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/about-enlight
123	EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	Infrastructure / Repository /	https://eosc.eu/
124	Geochemical Society	Geochemical Society	Union / Society	https://www.geochemsoc.org
125	Geotraces	An International Study of the Marine Biogeochemical Cycles of Trace Elements and Isotopes	Union / Society	https://www.geotraces.org
126	CGGB	The Commission on Global Geochemical Baselines	Union / Society	https://www.globalgeochemicalbaselines.eu
127	IUGS	the International Union of Geological Sciences	Union / Society	https://www.iugs.org/
128	GOSC	the Global Open Science Cloud	Infrastructure / Repository	https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/global-open-science-cloud/
129	OKF	Global Open Science Cloud	Union / Society	https://okfn.org/
130	OSDU Forum	The Open Group OSDU Forum	Union / Society / Software / Tool	https://osduforum.org/
131	ROR	Research Organization Registry	Registry	https://ror.org/
132	WorkflowHub	A registry for describing, sharing and publishing scientific computational workflows	Registry / Project	https://workflowhub.eu
133	RAiD	Research Activity Identifier	Registry	https://www.raid.org.au
134	Dataverse	Open source research data repository software	Project / Union / Society / Software / Tool	https://dataverse.org/
135	OData	Open Data Protocol	Software / Tool	https://www.odata.org/
136	ESFRI	the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures	Union / Society	https://www.esfri.eu/

N	Title	Full name	Scope	URL
137	EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	Infrastructure / Repository / Software / Tool	https://eosc.eu/
138	FID GEO	Specialised Information Service for Geosciences (Fachinformationsdienst Geowissenschaften)	Project	https://www.fidgeo.de/
139	GO FAIR	GO FAIR	Union / Society / Project	https://www.go-fair.org/
140	HIDA	Helmholtz Information & Data Science Academy	Project / Infrastructure /Training materials	https://www.helmholtz-hida.de
141	HIFIS	Helmholtz Digital Services for Science	Infrastructure / Repository / Project	http://www.hifis.net/#_blank
142	IGMAS	Interactive Gravity and Magnetic Application System	Project / Software / Tool	https://igmas.git-pages.gfz-potsdam.de/igmas-pages/about/#nutshell
143	ISIMIP	Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project	Project / Infrastructure / Repository	http://www.isimip.org
144	GAIA X	The Gaia-X European Association for Data and Cloud AISBL (French: association internationale sans but lucratif)	Union / Society / Infrastructure / Project	https://gaia-x.eu/
145	GeoKur	Curation and quality assurance of environmental research data for the use case of global land use data	Project	https://geokur.geo.tu-dresden.de/
146	AtMoDat	Atmospheric Model Data: Data Quality, Curation Criteria and DOI Branding	Project	https://www.atmodat.de/